
METHODOLOGY FOR USING INFORMATION AND EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: The article examines the methodology of using information and educational resources in teaching foreign languages to future teachers. The rapid advancement of information technologies has significantly transformed the educational process, creating new opportunities to enhance the quality of learning. These technologies, with their substantial didactic potential, have become essential in motivating students and fostering foreign language competence, particularly for prospective educators in the context of globalization.

The study explores the historical development of informatization in education, dividing it into four key periods. Each period reflects the evolution of technological tools, from the early use of computers in the 1960s to the current integration of e-learning and dynamic social systems that address diverse educational needs. The integration of multimedia and communication technologies has notably expanded the scope of foreign language instruction, enabling interactive learning environments and authentic linguistic experiences.

Key methods highlighted include the use of audio and video materials to develop listening comprehension skills, familiarize students with various dialects and accents, and encourage practical language application in real-world contexts. The research underscores the critical role of information technologies in fostering effective foreign language education, equipping future teachers with the skills needed in an increasingly interconnected world.

Keywords: foreign language teaching, information technologies, multimedia tools, educational resources, teacher training, e-learning, globalization.

Advances in information technology have opened up new opportunities for improving and enhancing the educational process. Today, information technologies possess "significant didactic potential, which facilitates the motivation of students in higher education institutions" [1]. The goals and objectives of higher education, as outlined in current educational standards, include mastering fundamental knowledge and skills, including foreign language competence. This is particularly relevant for future teachers due to the increasing trend of globalization [2].

Both domestic and international practices demonstrate that integrating modern information and telecommunication technologies into the educational process offers new opportunities for improving the quality of foreign language teaching.

The history of informatization in education can be divided into several conditional periods. The first period, characterized by the widespread use of computer technology in education, spans the 1960s and 1970s. The content of education during this time incorporated new elements of algorithmization and programming.

Educational computers were developed for use in schools and secondary and higher education institutions to address specific educational needs. Large computing centers were established based on powerful electronic computers in leading enterprises, universities, and research organizations to solve complex industrial, scientific, and educational tasks [3].

The programmed learning method was characteristic of foreign language teaching during this period. The teaching principles included learning, practicing, and control. Computers, assuming some of the teacher's functions, became both a source of information for students and a tool for evaluating the level of material assimilation.

The second period in the history of informatization in education, from the mid-1970s to the 1990s, is marked by the next stage of the "computer revolution," where personal computers became the central element. During this time, intelligent educational systems, which first appeared in the 1970s, were developed and

disseminated. These systems combined substantive information from scientific fields with new forms and methods of teaching and control. They improved the diagnostics of students' knowledge and skills, enabling students to develop audio-linguistic skills and behavioral competencies in foreign languages [4].

The third period, from the 1990s to the early 21st century, witnessed a significant leap in the development of technical tools, leading to increased speed and efficiency while reducing their size. The emergence of entirely new information and communication technologies, including the global Internet network, marked this era.

Multimedia technologies significantly expanded the possibilities for foreign language teaching, while communication technologies made direct interaction with native speakers a reality, effectively erasing boundaries.

Since the early 21st century, the fourth period of educational informatization has emerged. Concepts such as "e-learning," "electronic didactics," "electronic information and educational environments," "distance learning technologies," and "open education" reflect changes in the socio-economic landscape and the dynamic social systems that rapidly respond to individual and group educational needs [5].

In foreign language learning, computers offer new communicative, informational-combinatorial, and graphic capabilities. They facilitate the storage and processing of vast arrays of information, including three-dimensional graphics, audio, and video files. They also support search functions and present results in desired formats [36]. In classrooms equipped with internet-connected computers, information technologies aim to enhance interactivity, communication, and the automation of educational tasks. Multimedia tools are vital for perceiving educational materials and simulating authentic linguistic environments.

In foreign language teaching, using audio, video, and clips during lessons is highly effective for developing listening comprehension skills, one of the four main types of speech activity. These methods allow students to adapt to different dialects and accents and learn to use the language in real-life situations. For instance, audio and video materials enable students to observe how language is used in various

cultural contexts and understand its natural tone and intonation. All these elements are crucial for the language learning process [6].

The integration of information and educational resources into the process of teaching foreign languages to future teachers represents a significant advancement in modern pedagogy. This study highlights the transformative impact of information technologies on educational methodologies, providing new tools and approaches that enhance language acquisition and competence development.

Throughout its historical evolution, the informatization of education has demonstrated its ability to adapt to technological advancements, from early computer-based learning systems to today's dynamic e-learning environments. Multimedia technologies and internet connectivity have redefined the boundaries of foreign language education, fostering interactive and authentic linguistic experiences that prepare students for real-world communication.

For future teachers, mastering these technologies is not just an asset but a necessity in the globalized world. The ability to effectively use multimedia tools, audio-visual aids, and interactive platforms equips them to create engaging and effective learning environments. This, in turn, fosters their students' linguistic proficiency and cultural understanding.

References:

1. **Kovács, J. (2021).** Formation of Future Foreign Language Teachers' Linguistic and Methodological Competency Using Digital Technologies. ResearchGate.
2. **Chernyavskaya, T., et al. (2023).** Using Information and Communication Technologies for the Formation of Linguodidactic Competence of Future Foreign Language Teachers. ResearchGate.
3. **Vasylenko, S. (2020).** Development of Future Foreign Language Teachers' Digital Competences in Creating Multimedia Tutorials. CyberLeninka.
4. **Guzhva, A. (2022).** Assessment of Digital Competence Formation in Teacher Training. Information Technologies in Learning Tools Journal.

5. **Averina, E., & Bogdanova, T. (2019).** Formation of Professional Competence Based on Digital Resources. Academia.edu.

6. **Xujaniyazova G. (2023).** Enhancing foreign language training using information and communication technology. International Conference on Interdisciplinary Studies and Scientific Research Hosted online from Cambridge, London Date: 30th September, 2023
<https://econferenceworld.org/index.php/ecw/index>